

Tuning of Online Feedback Optimization for setpoint tracking in centrifugal compressors[★]

Marta Zagorowska^{*} Lukas Ortmann^{**} Alisa Rupenyan^{****}
Mehmet Mercangöz^{***} Lars Imsland^{*}

^{*} *Department of Engineering Cybernetics, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, email:*

`{marta.zagorowska,lars.imsland}@ntnu.no`

^{**} *Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Sciences, email:*

`lukas.ortmann@ost.ch`

^{***} *Department of Chemical Engineering, Imperial College London, email: m.mercangoz@imperial.ac.uk*

^{****} *ZHAW Centre for Artificial Intelligence, ZHAW Zürich University of Applied Sciences, Switzerland, email: rupn@zhaw.ch*

Abstract:

Online Feedback Optimization (OFO) controllers steer a system to its optimal operating point by treating optimization algorithms as auxiliary dynamic systems. Implementation of OFO controllers requires setting the parameters of the optimization algorithm that allows reaching convergence, posing a challenge because the convergence of the optimization algorithm is often decoupled from the performance of the controlled system. OFO controllers are also typically designed to ensure steady-state tracking by fixing the sampling time to be longer than the time constants of the system. In this paper, we first quantify the impact of OFO parameters and the sampling time on the tracking error and number of oscillations of the controlled system, showing that adjusting them allows good tracking without reaching steady states. We then propose a tuning method for the sampling time of the OFO controller together with the parameters to allow tracking fast trajectories while reducing oscillations. We validate the proposed tuning approach in a pressure controller in a centrifugal compressor, tracking trajectories faster than the time needed to reach the steady state by the compressor. The results of the validation confirm that simultaneous tuning of the sampling time and the parameters of OFO yields up to 87% times better tracking performance than manual tuning based on steady state.

Keywords: Online Feedback Optimization, controller tuning, sampling time

1. INTRODUCTION

By relying only on measured outputs, Online Feedback Optimization (OFO) provides computationally efficient solutions to complex problems with fast dynamics. OFO controllers steer a system to its optimal operating point without explicitly solving a nonlinear constrained optimization problem (Hauswirth et al., 2021a). OFO ensures reaching the optimum by exploiting properties of feedback control and iterative optimization algorithms, typically based on gradients for fast convergence. Thus, OFO implementations require tuning of the parameters of the underlying optimization algorithm, such as the time step between iterations, the length of a step in a single iteration, as well as weighting matrices (Hauswirth et al., 2021a). Successful applications of OFO include electric grids (Ortmann et al., 2023) and compressor stations (Zagorowska et al., 2022) where the parameters of OFO were set experimentally. Gil et al. (2023) proposed an iterative tuning method for the parameters of OFO in a distillation system, iteratively adjusting the step length

and weights with a fixed sampling time until the desired convergence of OFO was reached. However, the choice of the sampling time and the proposed tuning method were based on expert knowledge on the effect of the controller on the distillation system and thus application specific. In this work, we propose a method for tuning simultaneously the time step and the parameters of OFO without using explicit knowledge about their impact on the responses of the system.

Tuning of sampling time of controllers is classically done with respect to the timescales of the controlled system (Åström and Hägglund, 1984). Gil et al. (2023) chose the sampling time of OFO so that the controller runs on a slower timescale than the underlying dynamic system, thus ensuring timescale separation (Hauswirth et al., 2021b). Picallo et al. (2022) and Gil et al. (2023) indicated that large sampling time may lead to suboptimal performance of the controller especially in OFO using gradient-based optimization algorithms. At the same time, Belgioioso et al. (2022) have applied OFO with sampling time of minutes in optimization of building climate control operating on a timescale of hours, showing that OFO controllers can work without timescale separation. Thus,

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to find a trade-off between ensuring timescale separation and the performance of OFO based on gradient descent, we formulate a tuning optimization problem to find a sampling time that satisfies the requirements on the responses of the system.

The contributions of the paper are:

- Analysis of the impact of parameters of OFO on the performance of the controlled system, indicating that adjustment of the sampling time allows shaping the response of the controlled system;
- Development of a tuning framework for OFO so that the response of the controlled system has the desired properties with respect to error tracking and oscillatory behaviour;
- Demonstration of the tuning framework in an OFO controller for tracking suction pressure in centrifugal compressors without timescale separation.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the optimization problem for OFO tuning, which is then applied in Section 3 in a case study of compressor control. Section 4 analyses the impact of parameters on OFO performance, while Section 5 presents the tuning framework and validation results for the compressor. Section 6 presents conclusions and directions for future work.

2. ONLINE FEEDBACK OPTIMIZATION FOR DYNAMIC SYSTEMS

2.1 Dynamic system

The system to be controlled is described by a nonlinear differential equation:

$$\dot{x}(t) = f(x, u) \quad (1)$$

where $f : \mathbb{R}^s \times \mathbb{R}^p \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^s$ is continuously differentiable. The inputs $u \in \mathbb{R}^p$ are constrained by the physics of the system, $-b_2 \leq u \leq b_1$, $b_i \in \mathbb{R}_+^p$, $i = 1, 2$. The outputs $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are described by a continuously differentiable nonlinear mapping $y = g(x, u, z)$ where $z \in \mathbb{R}^n$ represents disturbances and $g : \mathbb{R}^s \times \mathbb{R}^p \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$. We assume that for a constant u , the system (1) reaches a steady state $x_s(u)$ such that $f(x_s, u) = 0$. Then we have:

$$y = g(x_s(u), u, z) = h(u, z) \quad (2)$$

where $h : \mathbb{R}^s \times \mathbb{R}^p \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is a continuously differentiable nonlinear steady state mapping. We further assume that the outputs y in (2) are bounded for any bounded inputs u and disturbances. We want to design an OFO controller so that the outputs (2) track a setpoint y_{sp} .

2.2 Online Feedback Optimization

Online Feedback Optimization (OFO) is designed to solve problems of the form (Piccalo et al., 2022):

$$\min_{u, y} \Phi(u, y) \quad (3a)$$

$$\text{subject to } y = h(u, z) \quad (3b)$$

$$u \in \mathcal{U}, y \in \mathcal{Y} \quad (3c)$$

where $\Phi : \mathbb{R}^p \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a continuously differentiable cost, and \mathcal{U} and \mathcal{Y} describe the constraints on the inputs and outputs, respectively:

$$\mathcal{U} = \{u \in \mathbb{R}^p : Au \leq b\} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathcal{Y} = \{y \in \mathbb{R}^n : Cy \leq d\} \quad (5)$$

where $A \in \mathbb{R}^{q \times p}$, $b \in \mathbb{R}^q$, $C \in \mathbb{R}^{l \times n}$, and $d \in \mathbb{R}^l$ are constant matrices (Häberle et al., 2020). Online Feedback Optimization (OFO) iteratively updates the inputs u of the system (1) to make the outputs y converge to a local optimum of the optimization problem (3). In particular, OFO makes use of measured outputs instead of full models to solve the optimization problem (Hauswirth et al., 2021a).

Optimization algorithm as a dynamic system The main idea of OFO is to treat optimization algorithms as dynamic systems, connected in a closed loop with the controlled system (1). In this work, we use an OFO controller with a constant step size $\alpha > 0$ (Häberle et al., 2020):

$$u^{k+1} = u^k + \alpha \hat{\sigma}_\alpha(u^k, y^k) \quad (6)$$

where y^k is the measured system output at time $k\Delta T$ with constant sampling time ΔT and $\hat{\sigma}_\alpha(u^k, y^k)$ is the minimizer of the constrained quadratic optimization problem:

$$\min_{w \in \mathbb{R}^p} \left\| w + G^{-1} H^\top(u^k) \nabla \Phi^\top(u^k, y^k) \right\|_G^2 \quad (7a)$$

$$\text{subject to } A(u^k + \alpha w) \leq b \quad (7b)$$

$$C(y^k + \alpha \nabla h(u^k)w) \leq d \quad (7c)$$

where w is an auxiliary decision variable of the same size as the system input u and $G \in \mathbb{S}_+^p$ is a positive-definite matrix $p \times p$. The matrix $H(u^k)^\top = [\mathbb{I}_p \nabla h(u^k)^\top]$, with $\nabla h(u^k)^\top$ is called *input-output sensitivity*. If the mapping h is known, $\nabla h(u^k)$ can be computed analytically. The matrix \mathbb{I}_p is an identity matrix of size $p \times p$. The gradient of the objective function $\nabla \Phi(u, y)$ is defined as

$$\nabla \Phi(u, y) = \left[\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial u_1} \cdots \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial u_p} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial y_1} \cdots \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial y_n} \right]. \quad (8)$$

Only the gradient of the objective function $\nabla \Phi$ in (7a) and the input-output sensitivity ∇h are necessary for OFO.

2.3 Online operation and tuning

The challenges of using the controller from (6) are two-fold: constraint satisfaction in (7) during online operation and tuning the parameters α , G , and ΔT in (6).

Physical constraints For tracking, $\Phi(u, y) := \Phi(y, y_{sp})$, and if there are no output constraints, finding minimum in (7a) allows steering the system to the optimum. We assumed in Section 2 that y is bounded for any u and z , so we can remove (7c) from (7). We also use the fact that u is a control signal with physical limits where (4)

is given by $A = [\mathbb{I}_p \ -\mathbb{I}_p]^\top$, $b = \begin{bmatrix} b_1^\top & b_2^\top \end{bmatrix}^\top$. Thus, we can remove constraint (7b) from (7a), effectively shifting the constraint from the optimization to the system. Then the control u_{applied}^{k+1} is given by a saturation:

$$u_{\text{applied}}^{k+1} = \max\{-b_2, \min\{b_1, u^{k+1}\}\} \quad (9)$$

where u^{k+1} is obtained from (6) as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_\alpha(u^k, y^k) = -G^{-1} H^\top(u^k) \nabla \Phi^\top(u^k, y^k). \quad (10)$$

The physical constraints on the system allows transforming the problem (7a) into (10), corresponding to OFO with the steepest descent algorithm (Hauswirth et al., 2021a).

Tuning The OFO algorithm from Section 2.2 assumes that there is a timescale separation between the system (1) and the controller (7) (Hauswirth et al., 2021a), i.e. the time interval ΔT between two consecutive control inputs u_{k+1} and u_k is longer than the time necessary to reach steady state. However, the experiments from Zagorowska et al. (2022) and Belgioioso et al. (2022) show that OFO performs well with short sampling times, with no timescale separation. Furthermore, Gil et al. (2023) indicated that ΔT should be chosen small enough, taking into account the accuracy of the sensitivity computation. A large ΔT would invalidate the approximation of the mapping h by the sensitivity at time $k\Delta T$ and thus lead to a suboptimal solution. Therefore, there exists a trade-off in choosing ΔT to promote the timescale separation and ensuring performance.

The performance of OFO from (6) depends also on α and G related to the optimization problem (7a). Gil et al. (2023) propose an iterative tuning procedure, by increasing α and decreasing G with a fixed sampling time until the system starts to oscillate. Thanks to the transformation from (10), it is sufficient to tune the product $\nu := \alpha G^{-1}$, reducing the number of tuned parameters to one. The value of ν affects how the control input changes from iteration k to $k + 1$ and corresponds to a step size in line search algorithms (Hauswirth et al., 2021a). Thus, a small ν will lead to slow convergence (Bertsekas, 2016) and thus a sluggish behaviour as the controller will need multiple iterations to reach the optimum. Conversely, a large ν may destabilise the system (Häberle et al., 2020; Hauswirth et al., 2021b). Finally, Belgioioso et al. (2022) have shown that the parameters of the optimization algorithm are connected to the sampling time, which indicates the potential in adjusting them simultaneously.

3. COMPRESSOR CONTROL

3.1 Compressor dynamics

Dynamics We design an OFO pressure controller in a natural gas compressor with nonlinear dynamics (Cortinovis et al., 2015):

$$\dot{p}_s = \frac{a_{01}^2}{V_s} (m_{\text{in}} - m) \quad (11a)$$

$$\dot{p}_d = \frac{a_{01}^2}{V_d} (m - m_{\text{out}}) \quad (11b)$$

$$\dot{m} = \frac{A_1}{L_c} (\Pi(m, \omega) p_s - p_d) \quad (11c)$$

$$\dot{\omega} = \frac{1}{J} (\tau - \tau_c) \quad (11d)$$

where p_s and p_d are the suction and discharge suction pressures respectively, a_{01} , V_s , A_1 , L_c , J are constant parameters defining the geometry of the compressor, m is the mass flow through the compressor, ω is the speed of the shaft of the compressor in rad s^{-1} , τ [Nm] is torque provided by a flow controller, τ_c is the reaction torque of the compressor, given as $\tau_c = \delta \omega m$ (Gravdahl et al., 2002) with $\delta = 0.00729$ capturing the internal geometry of the compressor (Cortinovis et al., 2015). The compressor map $\Pi(\cdot, \cdot)$ describes the pressure ratio across a compressor as a quadratic function of compressor mass flow and speed (Milosavljevic et al., 2020).

The value of m_{in} and m_{out} captures the external mass flows on the suction and discharge side, respectively. The mass flows depend on the pressures p_s and p_d , and external pressures p_{in} and p_{out} :

$$m_{\text{in}} = 0.4 k_{\text{in}} A_{\text{in}} \sqrt{|p_{\text{in}} - p_s|} \quad (12a)$$

$$m_{\text{out}} = 0.8 k_{\text{out}} A_{\text{out}} \sqrt{|p_d - p_{\text{out}}|} \quad (12b)$$

where A_{in} , A_{out} represent the inlet and outlet valve orifice areas and k_{in} , k_{out} the respective valve gains with values from Milosavljevic et al. (2020).

The initial condition for (11) is chosen as $p_s(0) = 1.015$ bar, $p_d(0) = 1.868$ bar, $m(0) = 60.45$ kg s^{-1} , $\omega(0) = 647.2$ rad s^{-1} and corresponds to a steady-state torque $\tau(0) = 323.6$ Nm.

Steady state To obtain the steady state mapping from (3b) we use $\omega = \frac{\tau}{\delta m}$ (Gravdahl et al., 2002) in (11c) to get $p_s = \frac{p_d}{\Pi(m, \frac{\tau}{\delta m})} = h(\tau, m)$ where m is treated as a measured disturbance and p_d is obtained from (12), taking $m_{\text{in}} = m_{\text{out}}$ for $p_{\text{in}} = 1.05$ bar and $p_{\text{out}} = 1.55$ bar.

3.2 OFO for compressor pressure control

To put the compressor control problem in the framework from (3), we set: $u = \tau$, $y = p_s$. The goal is to follow the desired suction pressure setpoint p_{sd} with the objective function (3a) formulated as:

$$\Phi(p_s) = 0.01(p_s - p_{sd})^2. \quad (13)$$

We assume no constraints on the suction pressure p_s , $\mathcal{Y} := \mathbb{R}$. The torque τ is physically constrained by $b_1 = 1000$ Nm, $b_2 = -300$ Nm in (9).

4. IMPACT OF OFO PARAMETERS

4.1 Performance metrics

We first analyse the impact of ν and ΔT when using the controller from (8) on integrated squared error over a tuning horizon t_F :

$$\epsilon(\nu, \Delta T) := \gamma_1 \int_0^{t_F} (p_s(\xi) - p_{sd}(\xi))^2 d\xi \quad (14)$$

scaled by $\gamma_1 = 10^{-8}$, and on number of oscillations $|F(\nu, \Delta T)|$, based on counting zero crossings (Thornhill et al., 2003):

$$F(\nu, \Delta T) := \{t_k \in [0, t_F] : p_s(t_k) = p_{sd}(t_k)\}. \quad (15)$$

4.2 Analysis of impact on performance

Impact on performance To show the relationship between ν and ΔT , we analyse the contour plots of the error and the number of oscillations obtained for the constant setpoint as functions of the parameters (right column of Fig. 1). The white line indicates where the error and the number of oscillations are equal. From the contour plots, we get that the smallest error is obtained for $\nu = 250$ and $\Delta T \leq 0.005$ (bottom right corner in Fig. 1c) which corresponds to the largest number of oscillations (bottom right corner in Fig. 1f). Conversely, a small ν and a large ΔT give no oscillations (top left corner in Fig. 1f), but increase the error (top left corner in Fig. 1c). The values annotating

Fig. 1. Impact of parameters ν and ΔT (in s) on the performance of OFO with the objective (13) and the corresponding control inputs, and a trade-off between the error (top right) and the number of oscillations (bottom right) as functions of parameters

the intersection line indicate that similar performance can be obtained for $\nu \in [75, 175]$ and $\Delta T \in [3, 9]$ s, with both error and oscillations approximately 7.2, which suggests that the parameters should be tuned simultaneously to find the optimum.

Impact on the system Figure 1 shows the impact of parameters ΔT (Fig. 1a) and ν (Fig. 1d) on the performance of the OFO controller for a constant setpoint. Figure 1a shows that increasing the time step ΔT leads to a slow response of the system for fixed α , because the OFO controller from (6) is applied infrequently (Fig. 1b). Decreasing the sampling time allows reaching the setpoint more quickly, at the expense of possible oscillations ($\Delta T \leq 0.05$ in Fig. 1a) or the inputs reaching saturation ($\Delta T \leq 0.005$ in Fig. 1b). Figure 1d confirms the results from Gil et al. (2023) who indicated that the value of the step size describes how much the control input changes during the sampling time ΔT . A small value of ν results in a sluggish behaviour ($\nu \leq 1$ in Fig. 1d and the corresponding control inputs in Fig. 1e), whereas larger values of ν improve the tracking performance but may lead to oscillations ($\nu \geq 10$).

The oscillatory trajectories in Fig. 1 show the numerical connection between ν and the derivatives in (10). From (10), we see that the control increments are:

$$u^{k+1} - u^k = -\nu H^\top(u^k) \nabla \Phi^\top(u^k, y^k) \quad (16)$$

The parameter $\nu = 1$ in Fig. 1a, so the controller reaches steady state when the optimum is reached and $H^\top(u^k) \nabla \Phi^\top(u^k, y^k)$ becomes close to zero (vanishing oscillations for $\Delta T \leq 0.05$ in Fig. 1a). If $\nu < 1$, the derivatives are mitigated, $\nu \|H^\top \nabla \Phi^\top\| \leq \|H^\top \nabla \Phi^\top\|$, and the controller increments in (16) are small, leading to sluggish behaviour ($\nu \leq 0.1$ in Fig. 1d). Conversely, $\nu > 1$ intensifies the effect of the derivatives, $\nu \|H^\top \nabla \Phi^\top\| \geq \|H^\top \nabla \Phi^\top\|$, leading to oscillatory behaviour ($\nu \geq 10$ in

Fig. 1d), in line with the interpretation as a step size in line search algorithms (Bertsekas, 2016, p.31).

5. TUNING AND VALIDATION

5.1 Optimization problem

To tune OFO, we solve the optimization problem:

$$\max_{\nu, \Delta T} \Delta T \quad (17a)$$

$$\text{subject to: } \epsilon(\nu, \Delta T) \leq \beta_1 \quad (17b)$$

$$|F(\nu, \Delta T)| \leq \beta_2. \quad (17c)$$

The objective (17a) is chosen to promote a large sampling time that would allow the underlying dynamics to reach the steady state within the time step ΔT . The constraint (17b) reinforces the reference tracking in OFO from (13) by restricting the time horizon to t_F , here $t_F = 200$ s. Conversely, the constraint (17c) enforces desired properties of the controller without modifying the reference tracking properties. Both constraints can be adjusted by choosing $\beta = [\beta_1, \beta_2]$, as suggested by Fig. 1 (right-most column), because the value of β_1 corresponds to setting a threshold for the error and β_2 for the number of oscillations.

To solve (17), we use a constant setpoint $p_{sd}^{\text{const}} = 0.925$ bar and two time-varying trajectories: a sinusoidal signal, truncated at 0.94 bar:

$$p_{sd}^{\text{sine}}(t) = \max\{0.94, 0.95 + 0.05 \sin(0.04t)\} \quad (18)$$

and a step signal

$$p_{sd}^{\text{step}}(t) = \begin{cases} 0.93 \text{ bar} & \text{if } t \in [75, 125] \text{ s} \\ 0.98 \text{ bar} & \text{if } t \in [0, 75) \cup (125, 150] \text{ s} \\ 0.95 \text{ bar} & \text{if } t \in (150, t_F] \text{ s} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

The tuned values from solving (17) were compared with a default OFO controller, with $\Delta T = 47.5$ s ensuring timescale separation and corresponding to the settling time of the compressor from (11) (within 5% of

Table 1. Tuned values for the three setpoints, with parameters in **bold** chosen for validation. The error ϵ is reported as absolute value and improvement from to the manual tuning

β	Constant setpoint				Step setpoint				Sinusoidal setpoint			
	ν	ΔT [s]	ϵ	$ F $	ν	ΔT [s]	ϵ	$ F $	ν	ΔT [s]	ϵ	$ F $
Initial	0.1	50	163.4 (-297%)	0	0.1	50	85.47 (-85%)	0	0.1	50	60.06 (-99%)	0
150, 50	40	99	136.03 (-231%)	0	0	99	86.29 (-87%)	0	0	99	60.75 (-101%)	0
37.5, 50	196.1	45.89	37.5 (9%)	0	183.1	74.95	37.3 (19%)	2	85.1	99	37.26 (-23%)	0
18.75, 25	202.1	22.88	18.7 (55%)	1	200.1	22.79	18.75 (59%)	4	199.1	80	18.69 (38%)	0
9, 12	223.1	10.9	8.96 (78%)	9	207.1	12.88	8.97 (81%)	9	229.1	10.37	9 (70%)	5
6, 20	468.1	5.78	6 (85%)	18	237.1	7.63	5.96 (87%)	12	278.1	7.52	6 (80%)	9
Manual	150	47.5	41.13 (-)	0	300	47.5	46.76 (-)	2	175	47.5	30.21 (-)	2

Fig. 2. Results of tuning for different setpoints

the final value (Bagge Carlson et al., 2021)) linearised around the operating points for $\tau = 323.6$ Nm. The system (11) with the controller (9) was simulated using `OrdinaryDiffEq.jl` (Rackauckas and Nie, 2017). The derivatives ∇h and $\nabla \Phi$ for solving (7a) were obtained using `Zygote v0.6.66` (Innes, 2018). The optimization problem was implemented in Julia 1.9.0 with Windows (x86_64-w64-mingw32) CPU: 8×11 th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-1165G7 @ 2.80GHz. The unconstrained optimization problem (7a) was solved using `OSQP v0.8.0` (Stellato et al., 2020). To overcome potential non-differentiability (Bachtar et al., 2016) when solving (17) with respect to the sampling time, we use a derivative-free solver, with a Julia interface `NOMAD.jl` (Montoisson et al., 2020) to `NOMAD 4.3.1` (Audet et al., 2022). The parameter $\nu \in [0, 10^3]$ is bounded for scaling purposes, and $\Delta T \in [5 \times 10^{-3}, t_F/2]$ reflects the physical setup of the compressor defining the smallest and the largest sampling time available.

5.2 Results for tuning

The results of tuning OFO for the compressor (11) are shown in Fig. 2 with the initial guess for parameters $\Delta T = 50$, $\nu = 0.1$ in red, the setpoint in dashed black (top row), and the bounds for the torque in black (bottom row). The initial guess for ν and ΔT was chosen following the recommendation from Gil et al. (2023), to start with

a small αG^{-1} , avoiding oscillations in the response and the control input without taking error into account, as indicated in Table 1. The values corresponding to the default OFO controller are in solid black lines. To achieve the desired performance, the values of β in (17) were applied in decreasing order, starting from $\beta = [150, 50]$, as suggested by Fig. 1.

Figure 2 shows that for $\beta_1 = 150$ and $\beta_2 = 50$, the constraints on the error and the number of oscillations have little impact on shaping the response ($\Delta T = 99$ in Table 1), and lead to a sluggish controller ($\beta_2 = 150$ in Fig. 2d). Prioritising the error $\beta_1 = 37.5$ while keeping the oscillation number high $\beta_2 = 50$, leads to oscillatory behaviour (third row in Table 1). Putting higher priority on the oscillations with $\beta_2 \leq 25$, and decreasing β_1 from 37.5 to nine allows achieving better tracking with damped oscillations, at the expense of decreased sampling time ($\Delta T \leq 12$ in Table 1). The oscillatory behaviour of the control signal in Fig. 2d confirms the importance of preserving the bounds on control signal in (9). Further restrictions on the number of oscillations, $\beta_2 = 12$ allow reaching a less aggressive response (Fig. 2d), at the expense of increased error.

5.3 Results for validation

To validate the tuning results, we track two trajectories for p_{sd} : a sinusoidal trajectory and a step trajectory

Fig. 3. Validation of the tuning parameters corresponding to constant tuning trajectory (Set 1), step tuning trajectory (Set 2), and sinusoidal tuning trajectory (Set 3) for two different setpoint trajectories

(dashed black in Fig. 3) reflecting possible setpoints for centrifugal compressors. The three sets of parameters for validation, Set 1, Set 2, and Set 3, were chosen from Table 1 and correspond to the smallest error obtained for constant setpoint, the smallest number of oscillations with the error below 10 for the step setpoint, and the largest ΔT and decreased error for sinusoidal tuning trajectory, respectively. The manual tuning for constant setpoint was also chosen because it gave the largest decrease in the error and zero oscillations compared to manual tuning with the step or sinusoidal setpoints. The initial condition for validation was set to $p_s(0) = 0.91745$ bar, $p_d(0) = 2$ bar, $m(0) = 80$ kg s⁻¹, and $\omega(0) = 700.5$ rad s⁻¹.

The results of validation are shown in Fig. 3 and Table 2 and confirm that solving (17) to find optimal parameters allows shaping the response of the system. Comparing the impact of the timestep ΔT on the performance, we see that a large value allows avoiding oscillations (Set 3 and Manual in Fig. 3a). Thus, the parameters obtained from (17) for the sinusoidal setpoint (Set 3) are comparable with the manual tuning preserving timescale separation. At the same time, a large ΔT leads to a sluggish controller and introduces delays in how the controller reacts (Fig. 3c). Thus, the parameters in Set 3 and obtained manually are only able to follow the slowly-changing parts of step validation trajectory (time below 250 s in Fig. 3a), as confirmed by large error values in Table 2. Conversely, smaller ΔT allows OFO to apply the control input more often and thus react to fast changes in the trajectory (Set 1 and Set 2 in Fig. 3a), decreasing the error (Table 2).

The performance for the parameters in Set 1 and Set 2 is further defined by the value of ν . The value of ν in Set 1 is almost twice as big as in Set 2, making the controller react quickly to step changes (orange in Fig. 3a), but introducing oscillations and controller saturation (orange in Fig. 3c). The oscillatory behaviour is due to including the setpoint in the calculations of the gradients in (4.1). From (13), we have $\partial^2\Phi/\partial y\partial y_{sp} = -0.02y_{sp}$ and thus a large change in the setpoint y_{sp} corresponds to a large change in the gradient $\partial\Phi/\partial y$ in (10). In Set 1, combining the large change in the gradient due to the setpoint with a large ν in (6) leads to the controller changing significantly within a small ΔT and introduces oscillations. At the same time, the parameters from Set 1 allow following the sinusoidal trajectory with the smallest error (first row in Table 2) because there are no abrupt changes in the setpoint trajectory.

Table 2. Error (14) for the validation trajectories, as absolute values and percentage improvement w.r.t. manual tuning (SM)

Validation Tuning	Step	Sinusoidal
Set 1 (S1)	29.98 (75%)	5.63 (94%)
Set 2 (S2)	41.51 (65%)	17.94 (80%)
Set 3 (S3)	201.07 (-69%)	139.51 (-53%)
Manual (SM)	119.2 (-)	91.27 (-)

5.4 Discussion and recommendations

The results from Sections 4 and 5 confirm that there is a nonlinear relationship between the sampling time ΔT and the step size ν in (7), suggested by Belgioioso et al. (2022). Simultaneous tuning of the parameters by solving (17) allows tracking the desired reference trajectory without relying on timescale separation. Instead of iterative tuning by adjusting directly ΔT and ν , which do not have explicit interpretation in terms of the responses of the system, solving the optimization problem (17) enables adjusting the thresholds β_1 and β_2 directly related to the error and the number of oscillations. As a possible choice of β_1 , we can take the error (14) obtained for the initial steady state and a chosen tuning trajectory:

$$\beta_1 = \gamma_1 \int_0^{t_F} (p_s(0) - p_{sd}(\xi))^2 d\xi. \quad (20)$$

The initial value for β_2 can be chosen with respect to the tuning horizon t_F , for instance $t_F/2$, allowing one zero crossing per two time units. Then both β_1 and β_2 can be decreased until the desired performance is reached.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

Online Feedback Optimization (OFO) controllers are an efficient method of steering a system to its optimal steady-state operating point by treating optimization algorithms as dynamic systems. OFO controllers have already been shown to work well in practice, with design and implementation tailored to specific applications. In particular, the performance of these controllers depends on the parameters of the underlying optimization algorithms, which are usually chosen on a case-by-case basis. In this paper, we propose a framework for tuning Online Feedback Optimization controller, finding a trade-off between the tracking performance of the system and sampling time constraints. The framework allows adjusting the step size

of the controller and the sampling time to achieve desired tracking properties, shifting the design of a controller from adjusting the optimization algorithm back to choosing the properties of the controlled system. We validated the framework in a pressure controller in a centrifugal compressor, achieving up to 87% times better tracking than the approach based on steady-state tuning.

The tuning framework proposed in this work consists in solving an auxiliary optimization problem with respect to the parameters of the OFO controller. We have shown that derivative-free methods allow tuning of OFO according to a chosen performance criterion. However, the tuning process required multiple iterations. Thus, there is potential in using other derivative-free methods, for instance based on surrogate optimization. Furthermore, choosing incorrect controller parameters during tuning may destabilise the system and safe learning algorithms could be used to tune the parameters.

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